

Supplementary Information for

***Operando* laser scattering: probing the evolution of local pH changes on complex electrode architectures**

Vitali Grozovski¹, Pavel Moreno-García^{1,*}, Elea Karst¹, María de Jesús Gálvez-Vázquez¹, Alexander Fluegel², Sathana Kitayaporn³, Soma Vesztergom⁴, & Peter Broekmann^{1,*}

¹Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, University of Bern, Freiestrasse 3, Bern 3012, Switzerland

²BASF SE, Global Business Unit Electronic Materials, Ludwigshafen 67056, Germany

³BASF Corporation, Global Business Unit Electronic Materials, Hillsboro, Oregon 97124, United States

⁴Department of Physical Chemistry, Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, 1117, Hungary

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to P.M.-G. and P.B. (email: pavel.moreno@dcb.unibe.ch, peter.broekmann@dcb.unibe.ch)

Figure S1. (a) Independent potential transient measurements exhibited the same characteristics regardless of the presence of the *pH*-sensing compound. (b) Comparison of the linear sweep voltammogram with and without *pH*-probe present in the electrolyte demonstrates its redox inactivity. All experiments were carried out with suppressor-containing plating baths (50 mM CoSO₄ in 0.5 M H₃BO₃, pH 2.5) on flat Co wafers mounted on a rotating disk electrode setup at $\omega = 100$ rpm. The galvanostatic depositions were carried out at $j = -1$ mA cm⁻² and the sweep rate of the LSVs was 10 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S2. Experimental setup for *operando* laser scattering investigations. The components of the setup are (a) electrochemical cell hosting the plating bath; (b) laser probe L1; (c) laser probe L2; (d) patterned die (working electrode); (e) Ag/AgCl_{3M} reference electrode; (f) Pt counter electrode; (g) stirring plate; (h) one of two xyz micropositioners and differential micrometer drives; (i) digital single lens reflex camera; (j) one of two DC laser power supplies; (k) potentiostat's display recording device (mobile phone, see Supplementary Videos); (l) potentiostat; (m) controlling computer.

Figure S3. Comparative top-down SEM images of die sections that were either (a) exposed or (b) not exposed to 1 min sample immersion at OCP in the Co plating bath (50 mM CoSO_4 in 0.5 M H_3BO_3). Cross-section SEM micrographs of die sections that were either (c) exposed or (d) not exposed to 1 min sample immersion at OCP in the Co plating bath for 1 min. The electrolytes contained both pH -probe and suppressor additive. Scale bars: 20 nm for all panels. The Co seed layer does not undergo significant damage upon contact with the electrolyte within the applied time interval.

Figure S4. A green laser beam (532 ± 10 nm, 5 mW, beam diam. 2.5 mm) is passed through a series of inhibitor- and pH-probe-containing Co plating baths (50 mM Co_2SO_4 in 0.5 M H_3BO_3) with pH values ranging from 2 to 6. Control experiments carried out with plating solutions containing no pH-probe are also shown.

Figure S5. A green laser beam (532 ± 10 nm, 5 mW, beam diam. 2.5 mm) is passed through a series of inhibitor- and pH-probe-containing Co plating baths (10-40 mM Co_2SO_4 in 0.5 M H_3BO_3) with pH values ranging from 3 to 4.7.

Plating bath
at pH 5

EDX spectrum

Figure S6. The precipitate was obtained from the *pH*-probe- and inhibitor-containing plating solution upon removal of the solvent and subsequent filtration. The plating solution was 50 mM Co_2SO_4 in 0.5 M H_3BO_3 with *pH* 5. The presence of Co species in the isolated precipitate was confirmed by EDX elementary analysis.

Figure S7. Precipitation phenomena are observed only when divalent cations are present in the plating bath. This confirms that complexation of the pH-probe at $pH > 4.5$ is mediated by Co^{2+} species in superconformal CoED.

Figure S8. Selected screenshots captured at different stages of the superconformal Co electrodeposition process by a camera placed in front of the Si die. The labels on the upper left corner of each subpanel indicate the time elapsed after the galvanostatic metal deposition was started. Scale bars: 1000 μm for all panels. The plating bath contained both inhibitor additive and pH-probe and the CoED was conducted at $j = -1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ and 100 rpm. Each adjacent patterned domain probed by L1 comprises an area of 0.265 mm^2 and is separated from the closest neighbours by 50 μm . The enhancement of the Tyndall effect occurs at earlier stages in comparison to the experiment described in Fig. 4 (at 300 rpm) because the mass transport limitations for the H^+ ion are more substantial at gentler stirring rates. Videos of TE enhancement from pH-probe aggregation experiments at 300 and 100 rpm are also provided.

Supplementary Videos 1 and 2.

Figure S9. Potential transient measurements corresponding to *operando* laser experiments shown in (a) Figure 4 and supporting Video 1 and (b) Figure S8 and supporting Video2, respectively.

Figure S10. The parallel patterned domains that in the probed surface regions are separated from each other by 50 μm spacings are accurately resolved by the TE-based colorimetry approach. The *ex situ* SEM image shows three such parallel patterned domains.

Figure S11. Linear sweep voltammograms recorded at 10 mV s^{-1} in additive-free plating baths (50 mM CoSO_4 in $0.5 \text{ M H}_3\text{BO}_3$, pH 2.5). Both patterned and non-patterned Co dies had the same geometric area exposed to the electrolyte. The samples were mounted on RDE sample holders that were rotated at 100 rpm during the potential excursions. The plot shows that significantly larger current densities from both H^+ ion reduction and CoED are achieved on samples bearing patterned fields.

Figure S12. (a) Selected contrast timeframes from *operando* scattering experiments as shown in Fig. S8. (b) Corresponding time evolution of contrast intensity. The data points represent the average of contrast intensity profiles measured along the dash lines of panel a, showing the progressive increment of local pH and agglomerate concentration. Scale bars: 1000 μm for subpanels in (a).

Figure S13. TE-based colorimetry experiments with alternating approaching and retracting cycles of the laser probe from the sample surface. The pictures were sequentially taken at advanced stages of the CoED when the surface pH had already surpassed the critical $pH > 4.5$. The intensity of the TE enhancement is clearly observed when the laser probe is positioned adjacent to the sample surface only. These control investigations were carried out on a non-patterned Co-seeded coupon. This confirms that the observed pH dynamics and resulting agglomeration presented in the main text originate from surface-confined processes. Scale bar: 1000 μm .

Supplementary Video 3.

Figure S14. TE-based colorimetry experiments with pH-probe-free plating electrolyte. No TE enhancement was observed throughout the CoED experiment. This confirms that the observed agglomeration presented in the main text originate from surface-confined electrochemically-driven pH-probe complexation and subsequent precipitation. Scale bar: 1000 μm .

Supplementary Video 4.

Figure S15. TE-based colorimetry experiments in the absence of electrochemically-driven processes. No TE enhancement other than that one due to background events was observed when no net charge was transferred through the solid-liquid interface. This confirms that the observed pH dynamics and resulting agglomeration presented in the main text originate from electrochemically-driven processes. Scale bar: 1000 μm .

Supplementary Video 5.

Finite element-based numerical simulations

In order to explain a possible mechanism of the Tyndall effect enhancement observed in Fig. 4 in the main text, numerical simulations utilizing the finite element method were employed. The simulations were carried out on a two-dimensional grid with a mesh resolution of 10 μm . The 600 μm wide, planar electrode that contained a 240 μm broad segment representing a patterned area was assumed to lie at the bottom of the simulation grid. Translational symmetry perpendicular to the simulation plane, as well as periodic boundaries in the lateral direction were assumed.

In the simulation, we treated two electrochemical processes, namely, Co^{2+} electroreduction,

and the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), which was assumed to take the form of a 2 e^- reduction^{1,2},

It was assumed that the partial current density of cobalt deposition, j_{Co} is determined by the Erdey-Grúz–Volmer–Butler equation

$$j_{\text{Co}} = -2F k_{\text{Co}} c_{\text{Co}^{2+}}^0 \exp\left[-\frac{\alpha_{\text{Co}} F \eta_{\text{Co}}}{RT}\right], \quad (3)$$

and thus depends linearly on the near-surface cobalt ion concentration $c_{\text{Co}^{2+}}^0$.

It was further assumed that the current density of HER is determined as^{1,2}

$$j_{\text{HER}} = 2F k_{\text{HER}} K_{\text{buf}}^{\alpha_{\text{HER}}/2} \left(\frac{(c^\ominus)^2}{c_{\text{H}^+}^0} \exp\left[\frac{(2-\alpha_{\text{HER}})FE}{RT}\right] - c_{\text{H}^+}^0 \exp\left[-\frac{\alpha_{\text{HER}}FE}{RT}\right] \right), \quad (4)$$

as a sum of anodic and cathodic contributions, where the anodic part depends inversely and the cathodic part linearly on the near-surface hydrogen ion concentration $c_{\text{H}^+}^0$. In Equations (3) and (4) the k terms denote reaction rate and the α terms charge transfer coefficients and F , R and T denote the Faraday constant, the universal gas constant and the temperature, respectively. In Equation (3), η_{Co} denotes the overpotential of cobalt deposition defined as

$$\eta_{\text{Co}} = E - E_{\text{Co/Co}^{2+}}^\ominus - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{c_{\text{Co}^{2+}}}{c^\ominus}, \quad (5)$$

where E denotes the electrode potential vs. the standard hydrogen electrode and $c^\ominus = 1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ is the standard concentration. These terms appear, with the same meaning, also in Equation (4). In Equation (4) K_{buf} denotes a buffer constant, as described in Ref. 2. The actual values of the parameters used in the simulation can be also found in Table V of Ref. 2; values of the k reaction rate coefficients were set to 100 times lower values for the non-patterned flat surfaces in order to mimic the blocking effect of the inhibitor additive³.

During simulations, Dirichlet boundary conditions were applied combined with numerical root-finding. That is, at each simulation step, by an initial guess for the value of E , new Co^{2+} and H^+

concentrations (and a corresponding current) were calculated for the near-electrode simulation mesh cells using the analytic integrals of Equations (3) and (4). The value of E was thus refined to match the current density set in a galvanostatic deposition scenario. Discretized forms of Fick's diffusion equations,

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2}, \quad (6)$$

were then solved, using the Crank–Nicolson method⁴, to propagate concentration changes over the simulation grid. The transport equations were solved for the $c_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ cobalt ion concentrations and for the Δc_{H} concentration difference,

$$\Delta c_{\text{H}} = c_{\text{H}^+} - c_{\text{OH}^-} \quad (7)$$

for which latter term a single diffusion coefficient was assumed. This allowed the consideration of acid-base equilibria in the boric acid buffer containing solution, and an accountable determination of pH profiles, as described in Refs.1, 2, 5. Values of the applied diffusion coefficients are also listed in Table V of Ref. 2; for the present case of a boric acid buffered solution, a $K_{\text{buf}} = 6.9 \cdot 10^{-8}$ value was used.

pH and Co^{2+} concentration profiles obtained by the described simulation method, with a set current density of $j = -1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ that matches the applied experimental value are shown in Fig. 5 of the main text and Fig. S16, respectively. While we note that no extra efforts have been made to quantitatively refine the model parameter values described in Ref. 2, the simulated results compare remarkably well with the Tyndall effect timeframes shown in Figure 4.

Figure S16. Selected screenshots of Co^{2+} concentration profiles captured at different stages of the simulated Co electrodeposition process. The labels on the upper central part of each subpanel indicate the time elapsed after the galvanostatic metal deposition at $j = -1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ had been started. The initial pH and Co^{2+} concentration in the plating bath at $t = 0$ was set to 2.5 and 50 mM, respectively. The blocking effect of the inhibitor additive adsorbed on non-patterned sample surface regions is achieved in the calculations by setting $k_{\text{Co}}(\text{patterned})/k_{\text{Co}}(\text{flat}) = 100$, where k_{Co} stands for the reaction rate coefficient for the CoED.

Although the applied model did not account for convection, the effect of stirring can, at least qualitatively, still be simulated. In order to do so, we included a finite diffusion layer assumption to the calculations. That is, we assumed that in each simulation step original concentrations are restored for grid cells that lie further than a certain distance from the electrode surface. Figures S17 and S18 show cobalt concentration and pH profiles obtained using an assumed diffusion layer thickness of 50 μm (a uniform diffusion layer thickness was assumed for all reacting species). Thus, comparison of Figures S16 with S17, as well as that of Figure 5 with Figure S18 straightforwardly reveal how stirring the solution (in accordance with our experimental observations) reduces the extent of near-surface reactant depletion.

Figure S17. Simulated Co^{2+} concentration profiles for a patterned wafer, assuming a finite diffusion layer thickness of 50 μm . All other parameters are identical to those employed in Fig. S16.

Figure S18. Simulated pH profiles for a patterned wafer, assuming a finite diffusion layer thickness of $50\ \mu\text{m}$. Contour lines show the (experimentally detectable) $pH = 4.5$ value. All other parameters are identical to those employed in Figure 5.

References

1. Gálvez-Vázquez, M.d.J., Grozovski, V., Kovács, N., Broekmann, P. & Vesztergom, S. Full Model for the Two-Step Polarization Curves of Hydrogen Evolution, Measured on RDEs in Dilute Acid Solutions. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **124**, 3988-4000 (2020).
2. Kovács, N., Grozovski, V., Moreno-García, P., Broekmann, P. & Vesztergom, S. A Model for the Faradaic Efficiency of Base Metal Electrodeposition from Mildly Acidic Baths to Rotating Disk Electrodes. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **167**, 102510 (2020).
3. Moreno-García, P. et al. Inverted RDE (iRDE) as Novel Test Bed for Studies on Additive-Assisted Metal Deposition under Gas-Evolution Conditions. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **167**, 042503 (2020).
4. Vesztergom, S. A short introduction to digital simulations in electrochemistry: simulating the Cottrell experiment in NI LabVIEW. *J. Electrochem. Sci. Eng.* **8**, 171-181 (2018).
5. Hessami, S. & Tobias, C.W. In-situ measurement of interfacial pH using a rotating ring-disk electrode. *AIChE J* **39**, 149-162 (1993).